

SELF-REGULATED AND SOCIAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT IN THE PRIMARY LEVEL AS STIMULI TO AN IMPROVED LEARNER'S PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Self-regulated learners appear to have better academic achievements than those who do not demonstrate self-regulated learning behaviors. The study is focused on describing the self-regulated and social learning environment of the students and how it affects their performance confined to the parents/guardians of Grade 2 pupils from the sections Matatag, Malinis, and Maaasahan of San Vicente Elementary School, San Francisco District, Division of San Pablo, San Pablo City. This study is a descriptive-correlational kind of research. 100 parent-respondents answered the survey questionnaires on behalf of their child last March and April. The respondents answered the survey questionnaire. The findings show that the self-regulated learning environment has a direct relationship between the Learners' Performances of the respondents. The data showed that there is a significant relationship between all listed variables and all the Learners' Performance. The findings show that the Social Learning Environment was completely correlated with the Learner's Performance. The study's findings might help them better understand and control their child's social learning environments. Help pupils keep track of their social learning abilities and habits. They may be able to evaluate how self-regulated learning and the social learning environment influence a student's capacities and learning habits based on the findings of the study. Future research should look at replicating the current study's findings with learners from different domains and learning contexts.

Keywords: Self-regulated Learning, Social Learning, Learner's Performance